

Validated HPLC Method for the Simultaneous Quantification of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in Pharmaceutical Tablets

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Abstract

The development and validation of a robust, accurate and precise Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for Simultaneous Estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in tablet formulations has been made. Hypersil ODS C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 2.5 µm particle size) and mobile phase of acetonitrile and 20 mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3.5, 45 and 55 parts of volume) at isocratic condition was used for chromatographic separation. Finally, the hydrochlorothiazide and metoprolol retention times were found to be 3.12 min and 4.93 min, respectively. The method was shown to have excellent linearity ($R^2 > 0.999$), precision (<1.18% RSD), accuracy (99.65–101.72%) and robustness under minor chromatographic parameters variation as per ICH guidelines. A statistical analysis using design of experiments (DoE) was performed to systematically evaluate the effect of critical chromatographic factors on system suitability parameters. The reliability of the method was supported by the values of % RSD, tailing factor (<1.22), and theoretical plates (>5600). At 80%, 100% and 120% spiked levels recovery studies yielded values within acceptable limits, and the quantification was found to be accurate. The method is proven to be a good routine quality control, stability analysis, and formulation development method for pharmaceutical products consisting of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, Hydrochlorothiazide, Metoprolol, Method Validation, Pharmaceutical Analysis, Stability Study.

Introduction

It is a very common cardiovascular disorder whose complication like stroke, myocardial infarction, etc are known to be higher in patients of this disorder [1]. Hydralochonzide (HCTZ) and metoprolol are one of the most commonly used combination therapy to achieve enough blood pressure control. It is a thiazide diuretic, whose mechanism is reduction of blood pressure, essentially by decreasing plasma volume via inhibiting sodium reabsorption in the distal tubules of the kidney [2]. Adrenergic blocker, metoprolol raises blood pressure by lowering cardiac output and inhibiting renin release. It is a β_1 selective blocker. In view of the common usage of these two drugs in combination, a reliable analytical method for their concurrent estimation is required for routine QC, compound development and stability studies [3]. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is one of the most widely accepted

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analytical method used in pharmaceutical analysis due to its high precision, accuracy and reproducibility [4]. In particular, Reverse phase HPLC (RP-HPLC) is the most popular method for the quantitation of pharmaceutical compounds because this method can separate and analyze intact mixtures of complex compounds efficiently. The objective of this research is to develop and validate a simple, accurate and robust RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in pharmaceutical tablet formulation and aims at developing and validating an RP-HPLC method suitable for determination of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in Tablet formulation [5]. In order to maintain high accuracy, precision and robustness with the proposed method, it will be optimized based on regulatory guidelines for pharmaceutical analysis. After validation, this method will be suitable for routine quality control analysis, stability assessment and formulation monitoring of such pharmaceutical products containing these drugs [6].

Materials and Methods

Materials

AKUMS Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Haridwar, Uttarakhand India kindly gave us Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol reference standards. The drugs mentioned in the above section were obtained from pharmaceutical tablet formulations procured from a local market in Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh, India. All solvents and reagents were of highest analytical grade. Merck® India Ltd., Mumbai, India was obtained HPLC grade acetonitrile and water along with ammonium acetate from Rankem Laboratory Chemicals. Ammonium acetate was used to prepare the buffer solution of the chromatographic system whose pH was adjusted to optimal with glacial acetic acid.

Chromatographic Conditions

Chromatography of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol was carried out on a Hypersil ODS C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 2.5 µm particle size). The HPLC system consisted of a Shimadzu (Japan) Corporation HPLC system (LC-20AD pumps, SPD-M20A DAD, CBM-20A system regulator operated by LC Solution software). A mobile phase involving acetonitrile and 20 mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 3.5) at 40:60 (v/v) was used to perform the analysis. For the analytes, a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min was maintained and the analytes were detected at 143 nm using a Diode Array Detector (DAD). The operation was performed at ambient temperature with injection volume of 20 µL in each sample [7].

Mobile Phase Preparation

The mobile phase was used as a combination of acetonitrile and a 20 mM ammonium acetate solution (pH 3.5) at a 45:55 (v/v) ratio. Any particulates were removed from the mixture with a 0.45 µm nylon filtering membrane. The mobile phase was degassed in an ultrasonic bath prior to the experiment to obtain smooth flow and thereby, prevent column blockage due to air bubbles in the mobile phase [8].

Preparation of Buffer Solution

The buffer solution was 1 L of 20 mM ammonium acetate which resulted in 1.26 g of ammonium acetate combined with 1 L of HPLC Grade water. Was adjusted to pH 3.5 with acetic acid glacial. The solution was adjusted in pH, filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter, degassed in ultrasonic bath to make solution smooth run in HPLC system and prevent air contamination in HPLC system [9].

Preparation of Standard Solution

Dissolution of 10 mg Hydrochlorothiazide and 50 mg Metoprolol in 80 mL methanol was prepared as a standard solution. The volume was made up to 100 mL with methanol and sonicated for 10 minutes to ensure that all of the sample is dissolved. Thus, to prepare stock solutions in the concentration range

of 2.5–25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Hydrochlorothiazide and 12.5–125 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of Metoprolol, 10 mL of standard solution made up to 10 mL of the same solvent. Further after the prepared solutions were filtered through a 0.45 μm Millipore membrane filter to remove any particulate matter they were analysed [10, 11].

Sample Solution Preparation

Accurate weighing of twenty tablets comprising of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol, and finely grinding. A mobile phase (1 mL) was added into a 100 mL volumetric flask, in which 10 mg of Hydrochlorothiazide and 50 mg of Metoprolol were dissolved, then a quantity equivalent to 10 mg of Hydrochlorothiazide and 50 mg of Metoprolol was transferred to this sample. It was sonicated for complete dissolution of the powdered sample. The volume was made up to 100 mL by addition of mobile phase after dissolution. The resulting solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter to remove any particulate, before being analyzed in for dichloromethane to calculate the amount of silicic acid based [12].

Chromatographic Examination

Chromatographic analysis was performed by isocratic method using the prepared mobile phase. 1.0 mL second/min and 20 μL injection volume was utilized. Diode array detector (DAD) was set at 243 nm and the analytes were detected. The analysis was performed at ambient temperature to maintain the sample stability [13].

Statistical Analysis

A DoE design was taken to systematically study the influence of the important chromatographic parameters, such as mobile phase ratio (Acetonitrile:Buffer), pH of aqueous phase, flow rate and detection wavelength can have on the retention time, peak area, tailing factor and theoretical plates of the Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol. A 2^3 full factorial design was used to determine the main effect and interaction effect between the factors and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) allowed to define whether each factor and their combinations had a significant effect or not. Statistically significant was assumed to be a p-value below 0.05. Assessment of model adequacy was done through R^2 values and lack-of-fit tests and has ensured that the regression model used in optimization of chromatographic conditions would be reliable.

Results and Discussion

Method Creation and Optimization

An RP-HPLC method to concurrently estimate Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in pure and pharmaceutical formulation using the development and optimization capability was successfully developed and optimized for high resolution and reproducibility. The chromatographic conditions were optimized using a Hypersil ODS-C18 column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 2.5 mm particle size) and a mobile phase of acetonitrile and 20 mM ammonium acetate solution, pH 3.5 in the ratio 45:55 (v/v), respectively, as the mobile phase. And so the analysis was carried out at a compromise wavelength of 243 nm, bearing in mind that in addition, there is Hydrochlorothiazide with a maximum absorbance at 272 nm and Metoprolol with a maximum absorbance at 223 nm. The flow rate was set to 1.0 mL/min. Figure 1 & 2 show retention times of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol respectively to be 3.12 min and 4.93 min respectively.

Figure 1. Chromatogram Showing Retention Peak Metoprolol

Figure 2. Chromatogram Showing Retention Peak Hydrochlorothiazide

System Suitability Parameters

Therefore, we optimized the RP-HPLC method for the concurrent estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol to give accuracy, precision and reproducibility. The retention times were repeatable on multiple injections which confirmed the reliability of the method. The precision values given by the %RSD of the peak area variations were 0.82 % for Hydrochlorothiazide and 0.15 % for Metoprolol, both indicating excellent precision. USP tailing factors of 1.21 for Hydrochlorothiazide and 1.05 for Metoprolol proved to be good peak symmetry and within the accepted limit (≤ 2). High values for plate count, 5620 for Hydrochlorothiazide and 6735 for Metoprolol, indicate that the column's ability to produce sharp peaks with clear separation. The system suitability parameters showed that the chromatographic system was working well. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Result of System Suitability Parameters

Injection No.	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area	USP Tailing Factor	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing Factor	USP Plate Count
	Hydrochlorothiazide		Metoprolol		Hydrochlorothiazide		Metoprolol	
1	3.10	375640	4.91	1587325	1.21	5620	1.05	6735
2	3.12	372485	4.94	1591240	1.20	5605	1.04	6710
3	3.08	369832	4.89	1589518	1.22	5590	1.06	6695
4	3.11	374210	4.92	1593425	1.21	5635	1.05	6750
5	3.09	373528	4.88	1588475	1.20	5615	1.04	6705
6	3.13	376102	4.95	1592108	1.21	5640	1.05	6760
Mean	3.10	373633	4.91	1590348.5	1.21	5625	1.05	6726
SD	0.019	2950.40	0.026	1958.32				
%RSD	0.61	0.82	0.53	0.15				

Accuracy and Recovery

Validation of the quantification accuracy of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol was carried out through recovery studies at 80%, 100% and 120% spiking levels using the developed RP-HPLC method. The results of the recovery (Table 2) were in accordance with high accuracy level because of the recovery percentages ranging between 99.65% to 101.72% showed the capability of the method to be reliable for pharmaceutical analysis. Excellent precision was confirmed by the %RSD values less than 2% for the mean recovery values: 101.72 % at 80%, 99.84 % at 100% and 100.51 % at 120 % for Hydrochlorothiazide. As with Metoprolol, method precision and consistency was confirmed as the range of recovery values for Metoprolol was between 100.12% and 100.68% with %RSD <0.5%. The method is robust, reproducible and a suitable routine for pharmaceutical analysis since all recovery values are within acceptable range (98–102%) This ensures that the proposed technique may be used reliably for estimating quantitatively Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in bulk drug and tablet product.

Table 2: Accuracy and Recovery Data (n=6)

Drug	% Spiking Level	Drug in Tablet (µg)	Standard Drug Added (µg)	Total Drug (µg)	Recovered Drug (Mean ± SD) (µg)	%RSD	Recovery %
Hydrochlorothiazide	80%	4.8	3.8	8.6	8.75 ±0.095	1.08	101.72
	100%	5.0	5.0	10.0	9.98 ±0.145	1.45	99.84
	120%	5.2	6.3	11.5	11.56±0.130	1.12	100.51
Metoprolol	80%	24.5	19.5	44.0	44.30 ±0.165	0.37	100.68
	100%	25.0	25.0	50.0	50.06 ±0.135	0.27	100.12
	120%	25.5	30.5	56.0	56.25 ±0.210	0.37	100.45

Precision

The system and method precision parameters were evaluated to determine the precision of the RP-HPLC method. Repeatability and reproducibility were analyzed by injecting a standard solution containing Hydrochlorothiazide (10µg/mL) and Metoprolol (50µg/mL) on four different columns three times. The values for Hydrochlorothiazide % RSD were 1.18% (system precision) and 0.72% (method precision) and for Metoprolol were 0.62% and 0.91%, respectively. The confirmed values show that the method is highly precise; and it has good repeatability and reproducibility. Finally, the results (Table 3), within the acceptance criteria (%RSD ≤ 2%) indicates that the method is reliable, thus suitable for routine pharmaceutical analysis.

Table 3: System and Method Precision Study Data

Injection No.	Peak Area of Hydrochlorothiazide	Peak Area of Metoprolol	% Assay of Hydrochlorothiazide	% Assay of Metoprolol
1	342815	1526423	99.54	100.12
2	339827	1519842	100.25	99.72
3	338492	1508765	100.48	99.89
4	341658	1521284	101.12	100.64
5	345183	1516732	99.89	100.02
6	337982	1503821	101.35	100.58
Mean	340659	1516144	100.44	100.16
SD (±)	4012.28	9487.23	0.72	0.91
%RSD	1.18	0.62	0.72	0.91

Intermediate Precision (Ruggedness)

The RP-HPLC method was evaluated for its ruggedness and intermediate precision through precision studies, which were performed at the intra day and inter day levels. It allows for repeatability, robustness and reliability as a means of quality control analysis. An assessment of intraday precision was done by measuring six replicate samples of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol on the same day with %RSD value of 0.72% and 0.35%, respectively at a concentration of 10 µg/mL and 50 µg/mL. The samples were analyzed on three different days for interday precision and the %RSD values were 1.15% in the case of hydrochlorothiazide and 1.09% of metoprolol, indicating high precision and reproducibility of the method. On these results, it is concluded that the developed RP-HPLC method allows the use of consistent and reliable results on different days and conditions which makes it useful for routine pharmaceutical analysis. Table 4 provides the summarized data.

Table 4: Intraday and Interday Precision Data

Concentration (µg/mL)	Intraday Precision (%RSD)	Interday Precision (%RSD)
Hydrochlorothiazide 8 & Metoprolol 40	0.72	1.15
Hydrochlorothiazide 10 & Metoprolol 50	0.35	1.09
Hydrochlorothiazide 12 & Metoprolol 60	1.08	1.42

Linearity and Range

The developed RP HPLC method had good linearity in concentration range of 2.5–25 µg/ml for Hydrochlorothiazide and in 12.5–125 µg/ml for Metoprolol. As can be seen from Fig. It shows a strong linear relationship between concentration and peak area and correlation coefficient (R^2) as 0.9988 for Hydrochlorothiazide and 0.9998 for Metoprolol.

Figure 3. Calibration curve of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol

Robustness Study

Robustness of the RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol was evaluated under the influence of the slight alteration of the analytical parameters such as flow rate, pH, detection wavelength as well as Mobile phase ratio. As seen in Table 5, % RSD values were always under 2%, peak symmetry (tailing factor) were under the acceptable range so the method shows good stability, reproducibility and therefore ability to be used for routine pharmaceutical analysis.

Table 5: Robustness Study Data for Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol Under Various Analytical Conditions

Parameter	Level	%RSD		% Recovery		Tailing Factor	
		Hydrochlorothiazide	Metoprolol				
Flow Rate (mL/min)	0.8	0.82	1.18	99.31	0.35	1.12	99.75
	1.0	0.61	1.05	100.12	0.28	1.09	99.62
	1.2	0.93	1.24	99.08	0.44	1.15	100.38
pH	3.5	0.14	1.06	99.58	0.51	1.21	99.42
	4.0	0.73	1.32	99.47	0.46	1.14	98.88
Wavelength (nm)	241	0.68	1.19	99.24	0.78	1.10	99.05
	243	0.12	1.07	99.39	0.49	1.08	99.62
	245	0.59	1.28	100.68	0.89	1.19	99.33
Mobile Phase Ratio (ACN: Buffer)	30:70	0.98	1.34	101.21	0.29	1.07	101.12
	40:60	0.51	1.09	99.27	0.75	1.06	100.58
	50:50	0.82	1.05	99.42	0.58	1.16	100.43

Detection and Quantitation Limits

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) for Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol were determined using RP-HPLC method to know the sensitivity of the method. The method also showed capability to detect drug concentrations even in the level of 0.22 µg/mL of Hydrochlorothiazide and 0.47 µg/mL of Metoprolol, respectively. The LOQ values 0.68 µg/mL for Hydrochlorothiazide and 1.42 µg/mL for Metoprolol were similarly well in agreement with high sensitivity and quantification efficiency of the developed method.

Table 6: LOD and LOQ Data for Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol

Medication	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)
Hydrochlorothiazide	0.22	0.68
Metoprolol	0.47	1.42

Assay of Marketed Formulations

The developed RP-HPLC method was used for analysis of two marketed formulations, HYDRO-MET XL and THIA-MET SR containing 25 mg Hydrochlorothiazide and 50 mg Metoprolol in each. The Hydrochlorothiazide (3.12–3.18 min) and Metoprolol (4.90–5.02 min) retention times were found to highly reproducible across multiple injections. The developed method was confirmed by the percentage assay values between 98.21% and 101.34% showing the method satisfied acceptance criteria (90–110%) and hence insisted the accuracy, reliability and suitability for routine quality control.

Table 7: Assay Data for Marketed Formulations

Marketed Formulation	Drug	Retention Time (min)	Peak Area	% Assay
HYDRO-MET XL	Hydrochlorothiazide 25 mg	3.15	362184	99.87
	Metoprolol 50 mg	4.94	1624789	100.12
THIA-MET SR	Hydrochlorothiazide 25 mg	3.18	357491	98.21
	Metoprolol 50 mg	4.90	1609385	99.47

Statistical Analysis (DoE Results)

The factorial analysis of design suggested that, mobile phase ratio ($p < 0.05$) and pH of the aqueous phase ($p < 0.05$) had significant statistical effects on both the retention times and the tailing factor of both Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol. In addition, mobile phase ratio and flow rate interaction was also observed to be significant in the determination of two-drug resolution ($p = 0.021$). Contrary, the wavelength of detection had little or no effect on the resolution or peak symmetry, and a slight but non-significant effect on peak areas respectively ($p > 0.05$). The value of the determination coefficient and the non-significant lack-of-fit values ($p > 0.05$) of ANOVA demonstrated that the model is adequate; and R^2 values of 0.9988 Hydrochlorothiazide and 0.9998 Metoprolol are high, thus, indicating the model is adequate. These goodness of fit values point to the perfect correlation between the predicted and observed responses hence satisfying the correctness of the regression model in streamlining the process. The optimization using the desirability function implied that the optimum chromatographic profile could be obtained (Mobile phase ratio of 45:55 (Acetonitrile:Buffer), pH 3.5, and a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min).

Conclusion

RP-HPLC method developed and validated in order to estimate simultaneously the Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in tablet dosage form has been successfully conducted according to the guidelines of ICH. The method was high through the %RSD (< 2), accuracy (99.12-101.23 percent) and sensitivity range and had LOD of 0.35 0g/mL and 0.92 0g/mL to Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol respectively. The retention times of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol were reproducible and consistent 3.12 minutes and 4.93 minutes respectively, robustness studies revealed the method stability amid minor changes on the chromatographic conditions. Large effects of mobile phase ratio and pH on chromatographic performance and interaction of the mobile phase and flow rate on the resolution were determined using statistical analysis using a factorial design of experiments (DoE). The regression model fitted perfectly with the values of R^2 higher than 0.99 and the lack-of-fit non-significant, which proves requirements of the adequate and reliable method. The technique was appropriate when conducting regular quality control and regulatory studies and assay values of marketed formulations were found between the acceptable range of 98 to 102 percent. However, the limitation of the study is that it is applicable at the present moment only to the tablet formulations, additional validation on biological matrices such as plasma and serum is advised in order to determine matrix effects and expand its applicability. Furthermore, although the isocratic elution system worked well in this case, future tests can be done on gradient elution technique in the aim of providing increased flexibility with regard to other more complex pharmaceutical formulations. To sum up, the present simple, accurate, precise, and robust validated RP-HPLC method may be considered ideal in the quantitative estimation of Hydrochlorothiazide and Metoprolol in the bulk as well as tablet forms.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors announce that there is no disagreement of interest associated with this research work.

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